

Research Paper

Evaluation of different thermal storage scenarios in an industrial polygeneration unit driven by waste heat and solar thermal collectors

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ABSTRACT

The paper aims to investigate and design a polygeneration installation placed in a biofuels industrial plant. The proposed configuration exploits the waste hot water stream coming from the integrated combined heat and power units, with solar thermal collectors serving as an auxiliary heat source. The Baseline Scenario includes an organic Rankine cycle for power production and an absorption chiller for cooling production at two temperature levels. Additionally, the available hot water stream feeds the biodiesel production line. The Baseline Scenario is analyzed parametrically under steady-state conditions and dynamically throughout the year. Moreover, various scenarios integrating both hot and cold water storage tanks, as well as additional solar collectors, are evaluated and compared with the Baseline Scenario in terms of thermodynamics and economics. The present work combines the concepts of waste heat recovery, polygeneration, and thermal storage in the industrial sector. Notably, the annual ORC electricity, digester cooling, and biodiesel cooling production are calculated at 1319.4 MWh_{el}, 1320.4 MWh_c, and 1717.4 MWh_c, respectively, for the Baseline Scenario. The scenario featuring a hot water storage tank volume of 50 m³ for heat supply to the biodiesel units, and a cooling storage tank volume of 30 m³ at the digester, appears to maximize thermodynamic efficiency. The digester cooling output is enhanced by 4.4 % compared to the Baseline Scenario, reaching the annual yield of 1378.4 MWh_c, while the digester cooling coverage is equal to 94.8 %. According to the cost-benefit analysis, this scenario achieves a payback period of 14.1 years. The most cost-effective solution is the incorporation of a single hot water tank with a volume of 20 m³, coupled with the biodiesel reactors. In this case, the tank serves as a backup unit, and the payback period is equal to 10.1 years.

1. Introduction

Industrial energy demand accounts for a significant portion of global energy consumption, driven by the need for heat, cooling, and electricity in various processes. This high demand poses challenges such as resource depletion, escalating energy costs, and substantial greenhouse gas emissions [1]. Thus, it is crucial to develop innovative solutions to address these issues. More specifically, waste heat sources from industrial processes can enhance energy efficiency by converting unexploited thermal energy into useful work or power [2]. Moreover, the integration of renewable energy systems, such as solar thermal collectors [3], as well as polygeneration [4], and energy storage units [5] can reduce the

reliance of industrial plants on fossil fuels, mitigate CO₂ emissions, improve energy efficiency, and maximize resource utilization. Together, these strategies provide a pathway toward a more sustainable and resilient industrial sector.

The biofuels business is an expanding industrial sector within the framework of promoting renewable energy sources and environmental sustainability. It is estimated that the global annual biofuels production can reach 53 billion liters by 2026. The raw materials for these production processes are agricultural waste, municipal waste, food waste, and used vegetable oils [6]. Biodiesel is a predominant biofuel, which can be combusted inside internal combustion engines, substituting conventional diesel as a share in the whole fuel blend [7]. The biodiesel production units, which incorporate catalyst-based reactions, provide a

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Nomenclature

A	Aperture area, m ²
a ₁	Linear heat loss coefficient, W/(m ² K)
a ₂	Quadratic heat loss coefficient, W/(m ² K ²)
C	Capital cost, €
c	Specific cost, €/m or €/m ²
CC	Cooling coverage, –
CF	Annual net cash flow, €
COP	Coefficient of performance, –
c _p	Specific heat, kJ/(kg K)
G _{b,N}	Direct normal solar irradiation, W/m ²
G _{b,T}	Beam solar irradiation on a tilted surface, W/m ²
G _{d,h}	Horizontal sky diffuse solar irradiation, W/m ²
G _{d,T}	Sky diffuse solar irradiation on a tilted surface, W/m ²
G _{r,T}	Irradiation due to ground reflection on a tilted surface, W/m ²
G _T	Global solar irradiation on tilted surface, W/m ²
h	Specific enthalpy, kJ/kg
K	Cost, € or €/kWh
K(θ)	Incident angle modifier, –
L	Length, m
LMTD	Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference, K
ṁ	Mass flow rate, kg/s
P	Pressure, bar or kPa
Q	Heat rate, kW
s	Specific entropy, kJ/kg K
SPP	Simple Payback Period, years
T	Temperature, °C
U	Overall heat loss coefficient, W/(m ² K)
UA	Overall heat transfer coefficient, W/K
V	Volume, m ³
X	LiBr mass concentration, –
Y	Yearly production, €/kWh or €/MWh

Greek symbols

α	Solar altitude angle, °
β	Surface tilt angle, °
Δt	Time step, min
ΔY	Yearly production difference, €/kWh or €/MWh
η	Effectiveness or efficiency, –
η ₀	Zero loss efficiency, –
θ	Incident angle, °
ρ	Ground reflectance, or density, kg/m ³

Subscripts & superscripts

0	Reference
a	Absorber
ACC	Absorption chiller
amb	Ambient
baseline	Baseline
c	Absorption chiller condenser or collector field
col	Single collector
cond	ORC condenser

cool	Cooling
cw	Cold water
driver	Pump driver
eH	High-temperature evaporator
el	Electrical
eL	Low-temperature evaporator
exp	Expander
g	Generator
hex	Heat exchanger
HT	High-temperature
hw	Hot water
in	Inlet
insul	Insulation
is	Isentropic
load	Load
loop	Hot water loop
LT	Low-temperature
m	Mean
mech	Mechanical
mix	Mixture
net	Net
nominal	Nominal
O&M	Operation & maintenance
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle
other	Other
out	Outlet
pipng	Piping
pump	Pump
r	Refrigerant
return	Return
rH	High-temperature refrigerant circuit
rL	Low-temperature refrigerant circuit
s	Strong solution
sb	Subcooling
sh	Superheating
solar	Solar
st	Stored in the tank
tank	Storage tank
th	Thermal
total	Total
u	Useful
w	Weak solution
wasteh	Waste heat stream

Abbreviations

CHP	Combined Heat and Power
COP	Coefficient of Performance
HT	High-temperature
LT	Low-temperature
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle
PVGIS	Photovoltaic Geographical Information System
TES	Thermal Energy Storage

low-toxic and eco-friendly alternative fuel by exploiting waste materials and promoting the concept of circularity [8]. Another promising biofuel is biogas, which is produced via anaerobic digestion utilizing biogenic materials. Biogas, a mixture of methane, carbon dioxide, and other gases, can be used in gas engines to generate electricity and heat [9]. In general, biofuel generation processes require both heat and cooling [8,10].

The Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) is a well-established and

promising technology for converting waste heat into power, capable of utilizing waste heat streams within the temperature range of 80–400 °C. The waste heat streams can be classified into gaseous streams, such as flue gas or exhaust air, and liquid streams, such as hot water or hot oil [11]. More specifically, Gutierrez et al. [12] performed the energetic and exergetic analysis of a recuperative ORC fed by the waste heat from a natural gas-powered internal combustion engine. The thermal efficiency of the ORC was found at 28.4 %, the electrical power at 146.3

kW_{el} , and the overall conversion efficiency at 11.58 %, using toluene as the working fluid. The largest exergy destruction percentage was determined for the condenser and was equal to 40.99 %. Escalante et al. [13] investigated thermodynamically and economically an ORC system aiming to recover the waste heat from a thermal power plant. After testing different working media, benzene seemed to be the most proper one, achieving an ORC power output of 1365.0 kW_{el} , while the overall energy and exergy efficiencies of the thermal power plant were enhanced by up to 22.34 % and 11.01 %, respectively. The economic analysis showed that the payback period was about 5.3 years. Moreover, Stainchaouer et al. [14] examined the utilization of the exhaust gases of a large oil tanker engine through an ORC. In the case of using R1233zd (E) as a working medium, the cycle's electrical load was defined at 741 kW_{el} , whereas the overall annual carbon emissions could be reduced by up to 7 %.

Another technology that can be fed with low-grade heat sources, such as solar energy, heat from biomass, or industrial waste heat, is the absorption chiller. These kinds of systems can drive various industrial processes that require cooling [15]. First, Lu et al. [16] studied in terms of thermodynamics and economics, an absorption chiller driven by industrial waste heat in the United Kingdom. The coefficient of performance (COP) reached the value of 0.86, when the generator and the evaporator temperatures were equal to 55 °C, and 10 °C, respectively. According to the economic investigation, the payback period was calculated at about 2.5 years, while the electricity cost savings were defined at £105 per kW_{th} of heat input. In addition, Du et al. [17] analyzed an absorption chiller fed by a waste hot water stream and cooled down through seawater. According to the research findings, the cooling capacity and the COP were defined at 3043 kW_c , and 0.77 on average, respectively, when the hot water temperature ranged from 80.7 to 98.7 °C, and the seawater temperature from 30.2 to 34.2 °C. The energetic efficiency of the waste heat recovery system was determined at 55.9 %, whereas the respective exergetic efficiency was about 86.1 %. Moreover, Bellos et al. [18] investigated an absorption cooling cycle powered by different types of solar collectors, including both non-concentrating and concentrating ones. In the case of using parabolic trough collectors, the overall exergetic efficiency achieved its maximum value, which was equal to 5.5 %. On the other hand, the lowest capital cost was defined when evacuated tube collectors were integrated.

In some cases, configurations that can provide more than one useful product are integrated into the industrial plants. Indicatively, Ayou and Coronas [19] examined two different heat pump configurations to provide useful heat at 75 °C, and cooling at 2 °C for the milk pasteurization process within the dairy industry. A vapor compression heat pump powered by photovoltaics and an absorption heat pump fed by a solar thermal collectors' field were investigated. The exergetic COP was found to be 0.54 and 0.30, for the case of the vapor compression and the absorption heat pump, respectively. The solar fraction was determined at 0.53 for the electricity-driven heat pump and 0.57 for the thermally driven heat pump. Semmari et al. [20] investigated the exploitation of the flare gas waste heat in a petrochemical industrial plant through an ORC and an absorption chiller, producing electricity and cooling, respectively. The energy and exergy efficiencies of the ORC were defined at 16 % and 35 %, respectively, whereas the overall energetic performance could reach the value of 59 %. Moreover, Alcantara et al. [21] analyzed thermodynamically and economically a trigeneration unit that produced electricity, heat, and cooling. The configuration was based on a natural gas internal combustion engine, while a heat recovery steam generator and an absorption chiller were integrated, too. The results indicated that the overall energy performance, the net present value, and the simple payback period were computed at 74 %, 269,390.40 \$, and 3.4 years, respectively. Xi et al. [22] examined and optimized energetically, exergetically, and exergoeconomically a trigeneration system, which produced power, heating, and freshwater. It included parabolic trough collectors, a storage tank, an ORC, an absorption chiller, a domestic hot water heater, and a water desalination unit. At

the final optimal design, the exergy efficiency and the cost rate were computed at 19.87 %, and 157.73 \$/h, respectively.

Another energy management solution that can be implemented in industrial facilities is Thermal Energy Storage (TES). The integration of TES systems, particularly when renewable energy systems are exploited, can enhance plant flexibility, overcome the mismatch between thermal energy supply and demand, reduce heat losses, and increase overall efficiency [23]. More specifically, Quinones et al. [24] examined the integration of solar thermal collectors along with a TES tank into the copper mining industry. Flat plate collectors, evacuated tube collectors, and parabolic trough collectors were examined assuming different aperture areas and tank volumes. It was concluded that the storage tank integration improved the solar energy contribution, especially during cloudy days and in the case of using parabolic trough collectors. Moreover, the proposed solar heat technologies seemed to be economically feasible compared to traditional fossil fuel-based units, whereas the flat plate collector was determined to be the most cost-effective option. Furthermore, Lalau et al. [25] investigated the utilization of latent heat storage units, based on Phase Change Materials (PCM), in industrial processes. The examined materials were adipic and sebacic acid and appeared to have an acceptable thermodynamic performance and lifespan. The melting temperatures were about 130–150 °C, degradation temperatures were greater than 180 °C, and volumetric energy density ranged from 75 to 95 and 75 kWh_{th}/m^3 . Kalbasi et al. [26] analyzed the integration of a cold water storage tank in a vapor compression chiller in Iran, which had extremely high temperatures during the summer. According to the research findings, the chiller's electricity consumption was reduced by 5.1 % during the peak hours, from 7 a.m. up to 11p.m. Finally, Hajabdollahi [27] studied a combined cooling, heat, and power system, which was made up of a gas engine for electricity and heat production, an auxiliary boiler for heat production, an absorption chiller, an electricity-driven chiller, and storage tanks for both heat and cooling loads. The optimization procedure revealed that the optimum design point, which included both types of storage tanks, achieved an enhanced total annual profit of 9.48 %, compared to the system without any storage tank.

According to the existing literature, both the researchers and the industrial stakeholders have paid significant attention to the implementation of waste heat recovery systems to produce multiple energy products, such as ORC modules, and absorption chillers, as well as TES units in industrial plants. However, there is a lack of studies that comprehensively address the integration of waste heat recovery, poly-generation, and thermal storage within industrial configurations. Additionally, according to the best of the authors' knowledge, the cooling storage tanks, despite being promising solutions for peak load shaving and shifting, have not been widely investigated. Existing studies mostly focus on storage tank applications within solar fields rather than coupling them with other industrial processes. Research on integrating multiple forms of thermal storage within industrial polygeneration configurations is lacking. The purpose of the present work is the detailed analysis and investigation of a polygeneration unit placed in a biofuels factory, which produces biodiesel and biogas. The extensive waste heat recovery potential in the form of hot water is exploited, providing useful heat to the biodiesel reactors, as well as feeding an ORC system, and a LiBr-H₂O absorption chiller with two evaporators. Therefore, the proposed installation generates four useful products, i.e., electricity, heat, and cooling at two different temperature levels. A solar field of high-vacuum flat plate collectors serves as an additional heat source. The current study presents a holistic approach to the management of the available heat sources in the industry, aiming at the production of various useful outputs and implementing TES solutions. The plant is studied thermodynamically under both steady-state and transient conditions, and economically, whereas the entire simulation model is developed in Matlab [28].

Table 1
Plant heat and cooling requirements.

Plant requirements	Values
Biodiesel thermal load	408.8 kW _{th}
Biodiesel cooling load	200.0 kW _c
Digester cooling load	166.4 kW _c

2. Material and methods

2.1. Description of plant processes

The industrial plant of MIL OIL HELLAS SA, which is located in Central Macedonia, Greece, produces biodiesel and biogas continuously throughout the day and year [29]. The produced biogas is burned in three combined heat and power (CHP) units, two with an electrical load of 1067 kW_{el} and one with 1562 kW_{el}. The generated electricity is consumed autonomously or sold to the national grid, while the CHP units produce useful heat in the form of hot water. The biodiesel production line requires heat, which can be covered by the CHP units, and cooling. The digester, which is necessary for biogas production, has significant cooling requirements during the year. It's worth noting that the heat provision to the biodiesel units is only a small portion of the heat produced by the CHP units. Significant amounts of heat from the cooling circuit or the exhaust gases of the CHP units are rejected to the ambient as waste heat. When the 3 CHP units are in full-load operation, the hot water stream available for utilization is at a temperature level of about 100 °C, with a total volume flow rate of 103.9 m³/h, resulting in a maximum theoretical heat recovery load equal to 3698 kW_{th}. The hot water is considered to be at a pressure level of 3 bar to be kept in the liquid phase.

The extensive waste heat recovery potential is exploited by implementing an ORC system and an absorption chiller. More specifically, the ORC is fed with the available hot water stream to produce electrical energy. At the nominal point of the ORC module, according to the manufacturer, the hot water flow rate is assumed at 75.5 m³/h, the hot

water temperature at 100 °C, the input thermal load at 2390 kW_{th}, and the nominal electrical power at 150 kW_{el}. Additionally, an absorption cooling system is proposed, which utilizes the available waste heat in the form of hot water to cover the cooling loads of the biodiesel units and the digester. The absorption chiller incorporates two evaporators covering the cooling needs at two different temperature levels, a low-temperature (LT), and a high-temperature (HT) one, i.e., the biodiesel cooling load at about 10–15 °C, and the digester cooling load at about 20–25 °C. In parallel, the installation of a solar field of 45 high-vacuum flat plate collectors (aperture area of 88.2 m²) is also proposed to assist the ORC and the absorption chiller with an additional hot water supply. This solar field aperture area is initially proposed by the plant authorities, taking into account space considerations. To conclude, the purpose of the present study is the proper exploitation of the available heat sources and the heat provision to all the integrated components of the poly-generation unit, while the incorporation of TES tanks is also tested.

It is highlighted that the biodiesel cooling load is considered to be equal to 200.0 kW_c, while the biodiesel thermal load and the digester cooling load are estimated at 408.8 kW_{th}, and 166.4 kW_c, respectively. The heat requirements of the biodiesel units are defined through a detailed analysis of the temperature data from the hot water circuits connected to the CHP units, while the digester cooling demand is calculated by analytical processing of the temperature data from cold water circuits around the digester, which contains glycol. During this analysis, the piping thermal losses are taken into account, too. The entire data processing is presented in detail in the Appendix A, while the heat and cooling requirements of the integrated systems are shown in Table 1.

2.2. Description of the various examined scenarios

In the current Section, a short description of both the Baseline and the Upgraded Scenarios is given. First, the Baseline Scenario includes the hot water streams coming from the 3 CHP units, the solar field of 88.2 m², the solar TES tank, the biodiesel units, the ORC, and the absorption

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of Baseline Scenario including the solar field, the biodiesel units, the ORC, and the absorption chiller.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of Upgraded Scenario 1 with 1 TES tank for both the biodiesel units and the absorption chiller.

chiller. At the Baseline Scenario, the total hot water stream, after mixing between the waste heat stream and the hot water stream from the solar field, is designed to be split into two parts. The largest portion of the stream is directed to the ORC, while the rest flow feeds, first the biodiesel units, and then the absorption chiller. This concept allows i) the ORC to operate at the highest possible temperature at the inlet to provide the maximum possible power output, and ii) the absorption chiller to be fed at a lower temperature, a fact that may not affect the performance negatively. The priority has been set to ensure the ongoing supply and functioning of the ORC, followed by the provision of necessary heat and cooling to the biodiesel units. The Baseline Scenario is depicted in Fig. 1.

In addition, some Upgraded Scenarios are also investigated, which include not only the systems integrated into the Baseline Scenario but also additional TES tanks with hot and cold water, as well as additional solar thermal collectors. More specifically, the Upgraded Scenario 1, which is shown in Fig. 2, incorporates a single TES tank to feed both the biodiesel units and the absorption chiller. The primary goal is to improve heat and cooling management by leveraging stored thermal energy. This setup aims to enhance the overall efficiency and stability of the system, particularly during periods of variable heat and cooling demands. Additionally, the Upgraded Scenario 2 features one TES tank dedicated to the biodiesel units, enabling autonomous operation. The primary goal of this tank is to ensure a continuous and stable heat supply to the biodiesel production line in the event of an accident or emergency. The Upgraded Scenario 2 is depicted in Fig. 3. Moreover, the Upgraded Scenario 3, which is illustrated in Fig. 4, includes two TES tanks, one for the biodiesel units and one specifically for addressing the cooling load at the digester. The hot water storage tank for the biodiesel units is integrated here as a strategic backup solution for the biodiesel production line. The cooling storage tank stores cooling capacity in the form of cold

water during the night when the cooling demand is lower. This stored cooling capacity is then used during the day when the cooling demand peaks. This approach helps to mitigate the performance drops of the absorption chiller during high ambient temperatures, ensuring that the digester's cooling load is met more consistently. Finally, the Upgraded Scenario 4 builds on the configuration of the Upgraded Scenario 3 by incorporating additional solar collectors to further enhance the system's performance. This scenario aims to maximize the utilization of renewable energy sources, improve overall energy efficiency, and ensure continuous operation even during high ambient temperature periods.

2.3. Thermodynamic modeling

2.3.1. Solar collectors' field and tank modeling

In this section, the mathematical modeling of the solar thermal collectors and the solar TES tank is presented. The produced heat in the collectors' field is stored in a TES tank, which is then mixed with the available waste heat stream from the CHP units to feed the various consumers, i.e., the biodiesel units, the ORC, and the absorption chiller. After that, the total hot water flow is split. More specifically, the flow that left the CHP units returns to them, and the solar loop flow returns to the storage tank. A schematic representation of the solar field is illustrated in Fig. 5.

The high vacuum flat plate collector MT-Power v4, manufactured by TVP Solar company [30], has been selected to be used in this industrial application, and pressurized hot water is used as the working medium. The technical specifications and the performance parameters of the collector according to a quasi-dynamic performance test based on EN ISO 9806:2013 [31] are displayed in Table 2.

The collectors exploit the global solar irradiation on the collector's tilted surface (G_T). The global solar irradiation on the collector's

Scenario with 1 TES tank for the biodiesel units

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of Upgraded Scenario 2 with 1 TES tank for the biodiesel units.

inclined surface is assumed as the sum of beam solar irradiation ($G_{b,T}$), diffuse solar irradiation ($G_{d,T}$), and irradiation due to ground reflection ($G_{r,T}$). It is described by the following expression [32]:

$$G_T = G_{b,T} + G_{d,T} + G_{r,T} \quad (1)$$

The beam solar irradiation on the collector's inclined surface ($G_{b,T}$) is computed considering the direct (beam) normal irradiation ($G_{b,N}$) and the incident angle (θ) by the following equation [32]:

$$G_{b,T} = G_{b,N} \cdot \cos(\theta) \quad (2)$$

Moreover, the sky diffuse solar irradiation on the collector's inclined surface ($G_{d,T}$), is defined considering the horizontal diffuse irradiation ($G_{d,h}$), and the surface tilt angle (β), which is assumed at 40° , as below [32]:

$$G_{d,T} = G_{d,h} \cdot \frac{1 + \cos(\beta)}{2} \quad (3)$$

Additionally, the irradiation due to ground reflection on the collector's inclined surface ($G_{r,T}$) is calculated by the following expression [32]:

$$G_{r,T} = \rho \cdot (G_{b,N} \cdot \sin(\alpha) + G_{d,h}) \cdot \frac{1 - \cos(\beta)}{2} \quad (4)$$

where (ρ) is the ground reflectance, which is assumed at 0.2, and (α) is the solar altitude angle. The definition of the incident angle (θ), and the solar altitude angle (α) are described in detail in Ref. [32].

The thermal performance of the solar thermal collectors is tested according to EN ISO 9806:2013 [31] based on the quasi-dynamic method [33]. The useful collector's heat per aperture area (Q_u) in [W/m^2] can be determined by the following expression [33]:

$$\frac{Q_u}{A_{col}} = \eta_0 \cdot K(\theta) \cdot G_T - a_1 \cdot (T_{col,in} - T_{amb}) - a_2 \cdot (T_{col,in} - T_{amb})^2 \quad (5)$$

where (η_0) is the zero loss efficiency, (a_1) is the linear heat loss coefficient, (a_2) is the quadratic heat loss coefficient, ($T_{col,in}$) is the collector inlet temperature, (T_{amb}) is the ambient temperature, while ($K(\theta)$) is the incident angle modifier, which is described by the following expression [34]:

$$K(\theta) = 1 - b_0 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\cos(\theta)} - 1 \right) \quad (6)$$

where (b_0) is a coefficient, that is found at 0.09, taking into account the incident angle modifier at 50° .

Additionally, the total available solar irradiation rate of the entire field ($Q_{solar,total}$) is determined as:

$$Q_{solar,total} = A_{total} \cdot G_T \quad (7)$$

where (A_{total}) is the total area of the solar field. The total useful heat rate of the entire field ($Q_{u,total}$), considering that (\dot{m}_{solar}) is the total mass flow rate of the solar collectors, and ($c_{p,hw}$) is the specific heat capacity of the hot water is determined as:

$$Q_{u,total} = \dot{m}_{solar} \cdot c_{p,hw} \cdot (T_{c,out} - T_{c,in}) \quad (8)$$

The thermal efficiency of the collectors' field is calculated as:

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{Q_{u,total}}{Q_{solar,total}} \quad (9)$$

Moreover, the solar TES tank is modeled through mixing zone modeling,

Scenario with 2 TES tanks, one for the biodiesel units and another one for cooling storage at the digester

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of Upgraded Scenario 3 with 2 TES tanks, 1 for the biodiesel units, and 1 for cooling storage at the digester.

Fig. 5. Solar collectors' field along the solar thermal energy storage tank, and the mixing with the hot water from the 3 CHP units.

Table 2
TVP high vacuum flat plate collector specifications [30].

Collector parameters	Values
Dimensions (Length-Width-Height)	(975-2015-51) mm
Area (A_{col})	1.96 m ²
Zero loss efficiency (η_0)	0.732
Heat loss coefficient (a_1)	0.50 W/(m ² K)
Heat loss coefficient (a_2)	0.006 W/(m ² K ²)
Incidence angle modifier (50°)	0.95

which is a common strategy in the literature [35]. It is considered that the tank can be split into 5 thermal zones, where the temperature value is considered to be uniform. The upper zone, where the temperature is higher and the density is lower, is called Zone “1”, while the lower zone is called Zone “5”. Carrying out the energy balance in each mixing zone, the differential equations for Zone “1”, Zone “2” (intermediate zone), and Zone “5” are described as:

$$\frac{\rho_{hw} V_{tank}}{5} c_{p,hw} \frac{\partial T_{st,1}}{\partial t} = \dot{m}_{solar} c_{p,hw} (T_{c,out} - T_{st,1}) + \dot{m}_{loop} c_{p,hw} (T_{st,2} - T_{st,1}) - U_{tank} A_{tank,1} (T_{st,1} - T_{amb}) \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\rho_{hw} V_{tank}}{5} c_{p,hw} \frac{\partial T_{st,2}}{\partial t} = \dot{m}_{solar} c_{p,hw} (T_{st,1} - T_{st,2}) + \dot{m}_{loop} c_{p,hw} (T_{st,3} - T_{st,2}) - U_{tank} A_{tank,2} (T_{st,2} - T_{amb}) \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\rho_{hw} V_{tank}}{5} c_{p,hw} \frac{\partial T_{st,5}}{\partial t} = \dot{m}_{solar} c_{p,hw} (T_{st,4} - T_{st,5}) + \dot{m}_{loop} c_{p,hw} (T_{hw,return} - T_{st,5}) - U_{tank} A_{tank,5} (T_{st,5} - T_{amb}) \quad (12)$$

The intermediate zones (3, and 4) are described similarly to Zone 2. More specifically, (ρ_{hw}) is the hot water density, (V_{tank}) the tank volume, ($T_{st,i}$) the temperature value of the mixing zone (i), (\dot{m}_{solar}) is the total mass flow rate of the solar collectors, (\dot{m}_{loop}) is the loop mass flow rate, (U_{tank}) the tank heat loss coefficient, and ($A_{tank,i}$) is the outer surface of each mixing zone. The temperature of the collectors' field total inlet stream ($T_{c,in}$) is equal to the temperature of the lower tank zone ($T_{st,5}$), while the temperature of the water stream that exits the TES tank to feed the various loads ($T_{load,in}$) is equal to the temperature of the upper tank zone ($T_{st,1}$).

Fig. 6. Hot water storage tank modeling.

Furthermore, it is important to mention that the hot water loop that releases heat from the storage tank is assumed to operate when the temperature ($T_{load,in}$) is greater than the waste heat temperature (T_{wasteh}), which is equal to 100 °C. The loop mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{loop}) is assumed to be equal to the total flow rate of the collectors (\dot{m}_{solar}). In this case, the stream exiting the storage tank, and the available waste heat stream are mixed:

$$\dot{m}_{loop} \cdot c_{p,hw} \cdot T_{load,in} + \dot{m}_{wasteh} \cdot c_{p,hw} \cdot T_{wasteh} = \dot{m}_{hw,total} \cdot c_{p,hw} \cdot T_{hw,mix} \quad (13)$$

$$\dot{m}_{hw,total} = \dot{m}_{loop} + \dot{m}_{wasteh} \quad (14)$$

To determine the unit performance during the day, the differential equations (10)-(12) are discretized according to the finite difference method, taking into account a time step (Δt).

2.3.2. Hot water storage tanks modeling

The modeling of the hot water storage tanks, which are suggested to be installed to feed the biodiesel units, and/or the absorption chiller, is presented in this section. The hot water storage tank modeling is shown in Fig. 6.

In the same way as the solar TES tank, these tanks are modeled through mixing zone modeling, considering 5 thermal zones. The upper zone is called Zone “1”, while the lower zone is called Zone “5”. Carrying out the energy balance in each mixing zone, the differential equations for Zone “1”, Zone “2” (intermediate zone), and Zone “5” are described as:

$$\frac{\rho_{hw} V_{tank}}{5} c_{p,hw} \frac{\partial T_{st,1}}{\partial t} = \dot{m}_{tank} c_{p,hw} (T_{tank,in} - T_{st,1}) + \dot{m}_{load} c_{p,hw} (T_{st,2} - T_{st,1}) - U_{tank} A_{tank,1} (T_{st,1} - T_{amb}) \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\rho_{hw} V_{tank}}{5} c_{p,hw} \frac{\partial T_{st,2}}{\partial t} = \dot{m}_{tank} c_{p,hw} (T_{st,1} - T_{st,2}) + \dot{m}_{load} c_{p,hw} (T_{st,3} - T_{st,2}) - U_{tank} A_{tank,2} (T_{st,2} - T_{amb}) \quad (16)$$

Table 3

Constant parameters for the ORC modeling [37].

ORC constant parameters	Values
Pump isentropic efficiency ($\eta_{is,pump}$)	70 %
Pump driver efficiency (η_{driver})	93 %
Expander isentropic efficiency ($\eta_{is,exp}$)	67 %
Expander mechanical efficiency (η_{mech})	97 %
Superheating (ΔT_{sh})	10 K
Subcooling (ΔT_{sb})	2 K
Cooling tower approach	6 K
Pinch point of the evaporator	3 K
Pinch point of the condenser	5 K

$$\frac{\rho_{hw} V_{tank}}{5} c_{p,hw} \frac{\partial T_{st,5}}{\partial t} = \dot{m}_{tank} c_{p,hw} (T_{st,4} - T_{st,5}) + \dot{m}_{load} c_{p,hw} (T_{load,out} - T_{st,5}) - U_{tank} A_{tank,5} (T_{st,5} - T_{amb}) \quad (17)$$

where (\dot{m}_{tank}) is the mass flow rate that feeds the tank, (\dot{m}_{load}) is the mass flow rate that feeds the load. The temperature of the hot water stream that exits the storage tank after the heat provision ($T_{tank,out}$) is equal to the temperature of the lower tank zone ($T_{st,5}$). Moreover, the temperature of the hot water stream that exits the TES tank to feed the load ($T_{load,in}$) is equal to the temperature of the upper tank zone ($T_{st,1}$).

2.3.3. Cooling storage tank modeling

The modeling of the cooling storage tank, which is suggested to be coupled with the HT evaporator of the absorption chiller and provide cooling to the digester, is presented in this section. The cooling storage tank modeling is shown in Fig. 7.

The cooling storage tank is also modeled through mixing zone modeling, considering 5 thermal zones. Similarly to the hot water storage tank, the differential equations for Zone “1”, Zone “2” (intermediate zone), and Zone “5” are described as:

$$\frac{\rho_{cw} V_{tank}}{5} c_{p,cw} \frac{\partial T_{st,1}}{\partial t} = \dot{m}_{tank} c_{p,cw} (T_{st,2} - T_{st,1}) + \dot{m}_{load} c_{p,cw} (T_{load,out} - T_{st,1}) - U_{tank} A_{tank,1} (T_{st,1} - T_{amb}) \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\rho_{cw} V_{tank}}{5} c_{p,cw} \frac{\partial T_{st,2}}{\partial t} = \dot{m}_{tank} c_{p,cw} (T_{st,3} - T_{st,2}) + \dot{m}_{load} c_{p,cw} (T_{st,1} - T_{st,2}) - U_{tank} A_{tank,2} (T_{st,2} - T_{amb}) \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{\rho_{cw} V_{tank}}{5} c_{p,cw} \frac{\partial T_{st,5}}{\partial t} = \dot{m}_{tank} c_{p,cw} (T_{tank,in} - T_{st,5}) + \dot{m}_{load} c_{p,cw} (T_{st,4} - T_{st,5}) - U_{tank} A_{tank,5} (T_{st,5} - T_{amb}) \quad (20)$$

where (ρ_{cw}) is the cold-water density. Furthermore, the temperature of the cold water that exits the storage tank to feed the HT evaporator ($T_{tank,out}$) is equal to the temperature of the upper tank zone ($T_{st,1}$), whereas the temperature of the cold water that exits the cooling storage tank to feed the digester ($T_{load,in}$) is equal to the temperature of the lower tank zone ($T_{st,5}$).

2.3.4. Organic Rankine cycle modeling

In the integrated ORC module, R1234ze(E) is utilized as an efficient

Fig. 7. Cooling storage tank modeling.

Table 4

Validation of the ORC model in Matlab with experimental data from the literature.

Examined cases				Reference [41]		Matlab model		Deviation	
Organic fluid	\dot{m}_{ORC} (kg/s)	P_{high} (bar)	P_{low} (bar)	$P_{\text{el,net}}$ (W)	η_{ORC} (%)	$P_{\text{el,net}}$ (W)	η_{ORC} (%)	$P_{\text{el,net}}$ (%)	η_{ORC} (%)
R245fa	0.02	7.05	2.09	139.11	2.84 %	139.11	2.83 %	0.00 %	0.47 %
R245fa	0.035	9.68	2.23	317.45	4.07 %	315.67	4.09 %	0.56 %	0.45 %
R1233zd(e)	0.02	6.82	1.82	174.78	3.67 %	175.21	3.69 %	0.25 %	0.38 %
R1233zd(e)	0.035	8.74	1.94	270.23	3.45 %	266.24	3.44 %	1.48 %	0.17 %

Table 5

Verification of the absorption chiller model in Matlab with data from the literature.

Temperatures (°C)				Gogoi and Konwar [43]			Matlab model			Deviation		
T_e	T_g	T_c	T_a	X_s	X_w	COP_{ACC}	X_s	X_w	COP_{ACC}	X_s (%)	X_w (%)	COP_{ACC} (%)
4	70	31	31	0.578	0.536	0.794	0.583	0.540	0.790	0.80 %	0.81 %	0.56 %
4	69	31	35	0.573	0.559	0.697	0.578	0.562	0.703	0.85 %	0.56 %	0.84 %
5	66	28	35	0.575	0.552	0.769	0.580	0.556	0.766	0.88 %	0.73 %	0.40 %
6	72	33	37	0.576	0.557	0.730	0.581	0.561	0.730	0.90 %	0.66 %	0.03 %
8	63	25	37	0.578	0.543	0.819	0.582	0.549	0.816	0.73 %	1.02 %	0.35 %
8	85	46	39	0.565	0.555	0.585	0.572	0.559	0.613	1.26 %	0.76 %	4.79 %
9	66	28	34	0.575	0.520	0.837	0.580	0.525	0.835	0.88 %	1.06 %	0.28 %

working fluid for low-grade heat sources [36]. At the ORC heat recovery system, the heat source inlet stream, which is hot water, with temperature ($T_{\text{hw,ORC,in}}$), transfers its heat to the organic medium. The load of the heat recovery system, which is the cycle's heat input (Q_{ORC}), is described by the following equation:

$$Q_{\text{ORC}} = \dot{m}_{\text{hw,ORC}} \cdot c_{p,\text{hw}} \cdot (T_{\text{hw,ORC,in}} - T_{\text{hw,ORC,out}}) \quad (21)$$

In the equation above, ($\dot{m}_{\text{hw,ORC}}$) is the hot water mass flow rate that feeds the ORC, ($c_{p,\text{hw}}$) is the water-specific heat capacity, and ($T_{\text{hw,ORC,out}}$) is the hot water temperature at the heat recovery system outlet. This outlet temperature is assumed to be 72 °C in all cases, as it is the minimum temperature required for the return stream to the CHP units. The organic working fluid enters the heat recovery system (state 2o), absorbs heat from the hot water, and becomes, at first, saturated liquid, then saturated vapor, and finally exits the heat recovery system at the superheated vapor state (state 3o). The heat recovery system load in terms of the working fluid can be described as:

$$Q_{\text{ORC}} = \dot{m}_{\text{ORC}} \cdot (h_{3o} - h_{2o}) \quad (22)$$

(\dot{m}_{ORC}) is the mass flow rate of the organic fluid. Before the evaporator, the working fluid enters the feeding pump (state 1o), increasing its pressure. Considering the pump driver efficiency (η_{driver}), and the isentropic efficiency of the pump ($\eta_{\text{is,pump}}$), the electricity input to the ORC feeding pump is described as:

$$P_{\text{el,pump}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{ORC}} \cdot (h_{2,\text{is}} - h_1)}{\eta_{\text{driver}} \cdot \eta_{\text{is,pump}}} \quad (23)$$

Then, the superheated vapor enters the expander to reach the cycle's low pressure (state 4o). The electricity production of the expander is described as:

$$P_{\text{el,exp}} = \eta_{\text{mech}} \cdot \eta_{\text{is,exp}} \cdot \dot{m}_{\text{ORC}} \cdot (h_{3o} - h_{4o,\text{is}}) \quad (24)$$

(η_{mech}) is the mechanical efficiency, and ($\eta_{\text{is,exp}}$) is the isentropic efficiency of the expander. At the condenser, heat is rejected to the cooling water. A temperature difference of 15 K is assumed between the condenser saturation temperature (T_{cond}) and the cooling water temperature at the condenser inlet ($T_{\text{cw,in}}$). The net electricity production of the ORC ($P_{\text{el,net}}$) is expressed by using the electricity produced from the expander generator minus the electricity consumption of the feeding pump by the following equation:

$$P_{\text{el,net}} = P_{\text{el,exp}} - P_{\text{el,pump}} \quad (25)$$

Consequently, the electrical efficiency of the ORC (η_{el}) is determined as:

$$\eta_{\text{el}} = \frac{P_{\text{el,net}}}{Q_{\text{ORC}}} \quad (26)$$

The input constant parameters of the ORC thermodynamic model are presented in Table 3.

2.3.5. Absorption chiller modeling

The mathematical formulation of the LiBr-H₂O absorption chiller with two evaporators is presented in this section. The LT evaporator is used to provide the required cooling load at the biodiesel units, and the HT evaporator is used for the digester. First, the system has two evaporating temperatures, the low evaporating temperature (T_{el}), and the

Table 6

Parameters of the cost-benefit analysis.

Parameters	Values
Solar collector cost per area (C_{solar})	500 €/m ² [47]
Piping cost per meter (C_{piping})	1.5 €/m [48]
Cost of insulation of the piping per meter (C_{insul})	30 €/m [49]
Electricity price (K_{el})	0.25 €/kWh _{el} [46]
Cooling cost for digester (HT) ($K_{\text{cool,HT}}$)	0.083 €/kWh _c
Cooling cost for biodiesel (LT) ($K_{\text{cool,LT}}$)	0.083 €/kWh _c

Table 7

Storage tank cost per examined volume [50].

Tank volume (V_{tank}) (m ³)	Tank cost (C_{tank}) (€)
1.1	1983
2.2	3054
4.4	5196
6.6	7338
10	13,000
20	18,200
30	22,000
40	26,000
50	29,900
100	50,940
200	92,540
400	175,740
500	217,340

Fig. 8. Hot water temperature that feeds the ORC, and the absorption chiller for different ORC hot water flow rate values.

Fig. 9. ORC heat input and power output for different ORC hot water flow rate values.

high evaporating temperature (T_{eH}), which are assumed to be 5 °C, and 15 °C, respectively, taking into account the plant's cooling requirements. The other three characteristic temperatures of the system are the generator temperature (T_g), the condenser temperature (T_c), and the absorber temperature (T_a). Assuming that the condenser and the absorber reject heat to the ambient, the respective temperatures (T_c), and (T_a) are higher than the ambient temperature by 5 K [38].

The LT cooling load, which is the load of the LT evaporator (Q_{eL}), is computed as:

$$Q_{eL} = \dot{m}_{rL} \cdot (h_{8L} - h_{7L}) \quad (27)$$

The HT cooling load, which is the load of the HT evaporator (Q_{eH}), is defined as:

$$Q_{eH} = \dot{m}_{rH} \cdot (h_{8H} - h_{7H}) \quad (28)$$

The absorber load (Q_a) is described by the following equation, applying the energy balance:

$$Q_a = \dot{m}_r \cdot h_8 + \dot{m}_s \cdot h_5 - \dot{m}_w \cdot h_1 \quad (29)$$

The generator load (Q_g) is described by the following equation, applying the energy balance:

$$Q_g = \dot{m}_r \cdot h_3 + \dot{m}_s \cdot h_4 - \dot{m}_w \cdot h_2 \quad (30)$$

The generator load (Q_g) in terms of hot water is defined below:

$$Q_g = \dot{m}_{hw,ACC} \cdot c_{p,hw} \cdot (T_{hw,ACC,in} - T_{hw,ACC,out}) \quad (31)$$

The generator load (Q_g) can also be described in terms of (UA), which is the product of the overall heat transfer coefficient and the heat exchanger area, and (LMTD), which is the logarithmic mean temperature difference, as below [39]:

$$Q_g = UA \cdot LMTD \quad (32)$$

The logarithmic mean temperature difference is calculated as [39]:

$$LMTD = \frac{(T_{hw,ACC,in} - T_g) - (T_{hw,ACC,out} - T_g)}{\ln\left(\frac{T_{hw,ACC,in} - T_g}{T_{hw,ACC,out} - T_g}\right)} \quad (33)$$

The condenser load (Q_c) is defined as:

Fig. 10. Absorption chiller heat input and high-temperature (digester) cooling load for different ORC hot water flow rate values.

Fig. 11. Total COP for different ORC hot water flow rate values.

$$Q_c = \dot{m}_r \cdot (h_3 - h_6) \quad (34)$$

Due to quite small pressure increments in absorption chillers, the pump work is considered negligible. A heat exchanger is also integrated to preheat the weak solution stream before entering the generator, through the strong solution stream exiting the absorber, and having a higher temperature. The heat exchanger's effectiveness is assumed to be equal to 0.75, and it can be described as:

$$\eta_{hex} = \frac{T_4 - T_{45}}{T_4 - T_{12}} \quad (35)$$

Moreover, the expansion valves are considered adiabatic, and thus the specific enthalpy is conserved. The mass balances are described by the following expressions:

Total mass flow rate conservation:

$$\dot{m}_w = \dot{m}_s + \dot{m}_r \quad (36)$$

Mass flow rate conservation regarding the LiBr substance:

$$\dot{m}_w \cdot X_w = \dot{m}_s \cdot X_s \quad (37)$$

(X_w), and (X_s) are the mass concentration of the weak and the strong solution stream, respectively.

Additionally, the refrigerant stream exiting the condenser is split, and the following mass balance is considered:

$$\dot{m}_r = \dot{m}_{rH} + \dot{m}_{rL} \quad (38)$$

Moreover, the refrigerant streams exiting the two evaporators are mixed before entering the absorber, and the following energy balance is defined:

$$\dot{m}_r \cdot h_8 = \dot{m}_{rH} \cdot h_{8HL} + \dot{m}_{rL} \cdot h_{8L} \quad (39)$$

Finally, the total COP is assumed as the ratio of the sum of cooling loads to the generator load:

$$COP = \frac{Q_{eL} + Q_{eH}}{Q_g} \quad (40)$$

The previous index evaluates the same way both cooling productions, neglecting the fact that the cooling is produced at different temperature levels.

Fig. 12. Absorption chiller generator temperature, absorption chiller water outlet temperature, ORC water outlet temperature, and final return water temperature for different ORC hot water flow rate values.

Table 8

Results at the nominal and the final design point.

Results	Nominal point	Final design point
ORC hot water flow rate	75.5 m ³ /h	73 m ³ /h
Absorption chiller hot water flow rate	28.4 m ³ /h	30.9 m ³ /h
LT cooling load	200.0 kW _c	200.0 kW _c
Hot water temperature after piping losses	99.9 °C	99.9 °C
Hot water temperature after piping losses & biodiesel thermal load	87.2 °C	88.2 °C
Hot water temperature that feeds the ORC (T _{hw,ORC,in})	99.9 °C	99.9 °C
Hot water temperature that feeds the absorption chiller (T _{hw,ACC,in})	87.2 °C	88.2 °C
ORC heat input	2384.2 kW _{th}	2305.2 kW _{th}
ORC power output	151.7 kW _{el}	146.7 kW _{el}
ORC efficiency	6.36 %	6.36 %
Absorption chiller heat input	552.5 kW _{th}	614.5 kW _{th}
HT cooling load	191.3 kW _c	237.6 kW _c
Absorption chiller generator temperature (T _g)	67.8 °C	67.9 °C
Absorption chiller coefficient of performance	0.71	0.71
Absorption chiller water outlet temperature (T _{hw,ACC,out})	70.0 °C	70.6 °C
Final return water temperature (T _{hw,return})	71.5 °C	71.6 °C

2.3.6. Validation

To ensure the accuracy of the proposed thermodynamic modeling, the models of the ORC and the absorption chiller are examined. The ORC module is simulated through Matlab [28]. The properties of the organic working fluids come from the CoolProp database, which is used in Matlab through the CoolProp Matlab Wrapper [40]. The results of the Matlab model, which are presented in Table 4, are compared to the data from the experimental analysis of Eyerer et al. [41]. The mean deviation of the produced electrical load and the cycle’s energy efficiency are defined at 0.57 % and 0.37 %, respectively. These values are considered low and acceptable.

A single-effect LiBr-H₂O absorption chiller is simulated in Matlab [28]. Matlab functions have been developed to calculate the enthalpy and the concentration of the LiBr-H₂O mixture based on curve-fitting equations, and can be found in Ref. [42]. The results of the developed model are compared to the results provided by Gogoi and Konwar [43].

Table 9

Thermophysical properties of all the state points of the ORC and the absorption chiller.

ORC state points	T (°C)	P (bar)	h (kJ/kg)	s (kJ/kg K)
1o	33.0	6.67	245.0	1.154
2o	34.1	20.03	246.7	1.156
3o	89.9	20.03	441.6	1.721
4o	54.8	6.67	427.0	1.743
Absorption chiller state points	T (°C)	P (kPa)	h (kJ/kg)	X (%)
1	33.0	0.876	77.5	54.5
12	33.0	5.035	77.5	54.5
2	57.9	5.035	129.4	54.5
3	64.7	5.035	2621.2	–
4	67.9	5.035	155.0	56.2
45	41.8	5.035	101.5	56.2
5	36.1	0.876	101.5	56.2
6	33.0	5.035	138.3	–
7L	5.0	0.876	138.3	–
7H	15.0	1.706	138.3	–
8L	5.0	0.876	2510.1	–
8H	15.0	1.706	2528.3	–
8HL	5.0	0.876	2528.3	–
8	5.0	0.876	2519.9	–

The results of the verification of the Matlab model are displayed in Table 5. The mean deviation of the strong solution concentration (X_s), the weak solution concentration (X_w), and the COP are determined at 0.90 %, 0.80 %, and 1.03 %, respectively. To conclude, the model is considered accurate enough.

2.4. Cost-benefit analysis

First, it is important to note that the technologies presented in the Baseline Scenario (ORC, absorption, and solar field of 88 m²) are already placed in the plant. That’s why the capital costs of these technologies are neglected. The techno-economic assessment presented in this section is focused on the integration of the additional components as suggested in the Upgraded Scenarios, i.e., the storage tanks and the additional solar collectors. It is highlighted, the present economic evaluation is a cost-benefit analysis for the additional integrated components (storage

Fig. 13. The impact of the ambient temperature on the ORC power production for different ORC hot water flow rates.

Fig. 14. The impact of the ambient temperature on the HT cooling production for different ORC hot water flow rates.

Table 10

Annual results of the baseline scenario.

Annual results	Values
Available waste heat	28790.0 MWh _{th}
Available solar irradiation	145.3 MWh _{th}
Solar useful heat	84.0 MWh _{th}
Biodiesel heat input	3581.1 MWh _{th}
ORC heat input	20197.1 MWh _{th}
Absorption chiller heat input	3664.2 MWh _{th}
ORC electricity production	1319.4 MWh _{el}
Digester (HT) cooling production	1320.4 MWh _c
Coverage of digester cooling load	90.8 %
Biodiesel (LT) cooling production	1717.4 MWh _c
Coverage of biodiesel cooling load	98.0 %

tanks, additional solar collectors), aiming to compare the current plant situation (Baseline Scenario) with the plant situation after implementing the additional equipment (Upgraded Scenarios).

The capital cost (C_0) is made up of the cost of the storage tanks (C_{tank}), the cost of the additional solar collectors (C_{solar}), the cost of the additional piping (C_{piping}), and the other costs (C_{other}) accounting for pumps and controls, foundation work, installation, labor as well as permits and contingency (unforeseen costs):

$$C_0 = C_{\text{tank}} + C_{\text{solar}} + C_{\text{piping}} + C_{\text{other}} = C_{\text{tank}} + C_{\text{solar}} \cdot A_{\text{solar}} + (C_{\text{piping}} + C_{\text{insul}}) \cdot L + C_{\text{other}} \quad (41)$$

(C_{solar}) is the solar thermal collector cost per unit area, (C_{piping}) is the piping cost per meter, (C_{insul}) is the insulation cost of the pipe per length, (L) is the length of the pipelines, which is estimated at around 100 m per storage tank, and (C_{other}) is assumed at 2 % of the main systems' costs.

As the capital cost includes the additional equipment, it is necessary to compare the benefits that the plant will receive after implementing the new equipment according to the Upgraded Scenarios with the benefits that would result from the technologies of the Baseline Scenario. The annual net cash flow (CF) is calculated by comparing the revenues of the proposed Upgraded Scenarios 1–4 with those of the Baseline Scenario. The revenues of the Baseline Scenario include i) the cost savings due to the ORC electricity production, and ii) the cost savings due to the cooling production of the absorption chiller for i) the biodiesel units and ii) the digester. By implementing the additional equipment (storage tanks and solar collectors) on top of the Baseline Scenario, the revenues change since the electricity production from the ORC and the cooling production from the absorption chiller change. Therefore, the annual net cash flow (CF) includes the yearly ORC electricity production difference ($\Delta E_{\text{el,ORC}}$) as well as the cooling production difference (ΔY_{cool}) between the Upgraded and Baseline Scenario, minus the annual costs for operation and maintenance. It is important to note that the revenues from the absorption chiller are determined by the savings achieved by not utilizing a conventional vapor compression chiller. Therefore, the annual net cash flow (CF) is calculated as:

$$CF = K_{\text{el}} \cdot \Delta Y_{\text{el,ORC}} + K_{\text{cool,LT}} \cdot \Delta Y_{\text{cool,LT}} + K_{\text{cool,HT}} \cdot \Delta Y_{\text{cool,HT}} - K_{\text{O\&M}} \quad (42)$$

where (K_{el}) is the cost of electricity, (K_{cool}) is the cost of cooling, ($K_{\text{O\&M}}$) is the operation and maintenance costs, which are considered as 1 % of the capital cost [44], whereas ($\Delta E_{\text{el,ORC}}$) is the ORC electricity production difference between the examined Upgraded and Baseline Scenario in [kWh_{el}]:

$$\Delta Y_{\text{el,ORC}} = Y_{\text{el,ORC}} - Y_{\text{el,ORC,baseline}} \quad (43)$$

(ΔY_{cool}) is the cooling production difference between the examined Upgraded and Baseline Scenario in [kWh_c]:

$$\Delta Y_{\text{cool}} = Y_{\text{cool}} - Y_{\text{cool,baseline}} \quad (44)$$

The subscripts “LT” and “HT” refer to the LT, and HT cooling operations, respectively. Moreover, the refrigeration cost can be calculated as the ratio of the electricity cost to the mean COP of a conventional vapor compression chiller, which is assumed at 3 [45], and is written as:

$$K_{\text{cool}} = \frac{K_{\text{el}}}{\text{COP}_m} \quad (45)$$

The simple payback period (SPP) is calculated as:

$$\text{SPP} = \frac{C_0}{\text{CF}} \quad (46)$$

The simple payback period presupposes that the annual net cash flow numbers should remain constant throughout the duration of the investment. All the associated costs are presented in Table 6. The cost of the solar collectors is provided by TVP, the cost of the piping and its insulation is based on market data, the electricity price is determined at 0.25 €/kWh_{el} by assuming the average of the two previous years [46], while the storage tank costs are provided in Table 7 and are based on suppliers' prices.

2.5. Simulation strategy

The examined polygeneration unit is investigated

Fig. 15. Hot water temperature after the mixing between waste heat and solar heat during the year for the Baseline Scenario.

Fig. 16. ORC power output during the year for the Baseline Scenario.

thermodynamically under both steady and unsteady conditions, as well as economically. The first step of the analysis involves the parametric analysis of the Baseline Scenario under steady-state conditions. During this analysis, the contribution of solar thermal collectors is neglected because i) the produced solar heat is much lower than the waste heat, ii) it is not able to increase the waste heat source temperature significantly (< 1 K increase), and iii) under steady-state conditions it cannot be evaluated effectively (owed to its stochastic operational profile). The hot water flow rate that feeds the ORC and the absorption chiller is an essential parameter that must be carefully handled to meet both electricity and cooling requirements. In other words, this parametric analysis aims to show how the electricity and cooling production loads vary as the flow separation design changes. The ORC hot water flow rate varies within the range of 70 to 76.5 m³/h, knowing that the nominal value is equal to 75.5 m³/h. Using this parametric analysis, the final design point for the hot water flow rate is defined, assuming an ambient temperature of 25 °C. Furthermore, the steady-state analysis includes

the investigation of the system performance for different values of ambient temperature.

Then, a dynamic simulation of the Baseline Scenario is conducted for a whole year. Under dynamic conditions, the contribution of the solar thermal collectors and the ambient temperature variability that affects the operation of the ORC and the absorption chiller are taken into account. The ambient temperature variation during the day and the year influences the ORC condensation temperature, as well as the temperature of the absorber and the condenser of the absorption chiller. As the temperature of the absorber and condenser increases during the summer, COP reduces, and the chiller cannot provide the nominal cooling capacities, particularly for the digester (HT cooling load). Thus, the generator temperature also varies, aiming to achieve the maximum possible cooling production loads. Additionally, several Upgraded Scenarios that include both hot and cold water storage tank volumes are investigated dynamically, examining different storage tank volume values. Moreover, the installation of additional solar thermal collectors

Fig. 17. HT (digester) and LT (biodiesel) cooling load during the year for the Baseline Scenario.

Fig. 18. Hot water temperature at the inlet and the outlet of various systems during the year for the Baseline Scenario.

is tested. The performance of both the LT and HT cooling units is evaluated through the cooling coverage (CC), which is the ratio of the actual yearly cooling production (Y_{cool}) to the theoretical yearly cooling production under nominal conditions ($Y_{cool,nominal}$) as below:

$$CC = \frac{Y_{cool}}{Y_{cool,nominal}} \quad (47)$$

The various scenarios are evaluated and compared in terms of economics, too. It is worth mentioning that the generator (UA) value is computed at 70 kW_{th}/K, based on preliminary calculations. Moreover, the tank’s overall heat loss coefficient (U_{tank}) is assumed at 0.5 W/m²K [51], the dynamic simulation time step (Δt) is set at 5 min, whereas a temperature of 5 K is considered in the hot water circuit that feeds the

biodiesel units. Furthermore, the solar TES tank volume is defined taking into account the empirical rule that the ratio of the solar aperture area to the respective tank volume is about 80 [35]. Finally, the local ambient temperature and solar irradiation data have been extracted from the database of the Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS) [52], while the entire simulation model has been developed in Matlab [28].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Parametric analysis of the baseline scenario

The first step of the parametric analysis under steady-state conditions focuses on the impact of the hot water flow rate that feeds the ORC

Fig. 19. HT (digester) and LT (biodiesel) cooling load during the 20th and 21st of July for the Baseline Scenario.

Table 11

Annual results of upgraded scenario 1 with 1 TES tank for both the biodiesel units and the absorption chiller for various tank volumes.

Hot water storage tank volume for both the biodiesel units and the absorption chiller (m ³)	10	20	50	100	200	400
ORC heat input (MWh _{th})	20197.2	20197.2	20197.1	20197.0	20196.9	20196.8
Absorption chiller heat input (MWh _{th})	3605.8	3604.5	3600.8	3595.8	3585.6	3573.6
ORC electricity production (MWh _{el})	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4
Digester (HT) cooling production (MWh _c)	1272.0	1271.5	1271.4	1274.8	1279.5	1281.3
Coverage of digester cooling load	87.5 %	87.4 %	87.4 %	87.7 %	88.0 %	88.1 %
Biodiesel (LT) cooling production (MWh _c)	1711.7	1711.4	1709.6	1705.3	1697.8	1691.2
Coverage of biodiesel cooling load	97.7 %	97.7 %	97.6 %	97.3 %	96.9 %	96.5 %

Table 12

Annual results of upgraded scenario 2 with 1 TES tank for the biodiesel units for various tank volumes.

Hot water storage tank volume for the biodiesel units (m ³)	10	20	50	100	200	400
ORC heat input (MWh _{th})	20197.1	20197.1	20197.1	20197.0	20197.0	20197.0
Absorption chiller heat input (MWh _{th})	3661.6	3696.6	3700.4	3696.3	3692.0	3678.8
ORC electricity production (MWh _{el})	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4
Digester (HT) cooling production (MWh _c)	1317.9	1348.8	1352.3	1349.2	1346.4	1335.8
Coverage of digester cooling load	90.6 %	92.8 %	93.0 %	92.8 %	92.6 %	91.9 %
Biodiesel (LT) cooling production (MWh _c)	1717.4	1717.4	1717.3	1716.8	1716.0	1715.0
Coverage of biodiesel cooling load	98.0 %	98.0 %	98.0 %	98.0 %	97.9 %	97.9 %

Table 13

Hours of autonomous operation for different biodiesel hot water tank volumes, and temperature limits.

Biodiesel hot water tank volumes	Hot water temperature limit of 90 °C to feed the biodiesel units	Hot water temperature limit of 87 °C to feed the biodiesel units
V _{tank} = 10 m ³	0.17 h	0.25 h
V _{tank} = 20 m ³	0.17 h	0.42 h
V _{tank} = 50 m ³	0.33 h	0.75 h
V _{tank} = 100 m ³	0.50 h	1.42 h
V _{tank} = 200 m ³	0.92 h	2.67 h
V _{tank} = 400 m ³	1.75 h	5.08 h

and the absorption chiller. Taking into consideration that the total available hot water flow rate is equal to 103.9 m³/h, the hot water flow rate that feeds the ORC varies, while the absorption chiller and the biodiesel units are driven by the rest flow. Throughout these simulations, the LT cooling load (biodiesel cooling demand) is set constant and equal to 200.0 kW_c for all cases, as this cooling demand has been prioritized by the industry. First, Fig. 8 shows that as the hot water flow rate supplying the ORC increases, the temperature of the stream entering the absorption chiller decreases. The remaining hot water flow is directed to the biodiesel production line before reaching the absorption chiller. A lower flow rate in the stream that feeds the biodiesel units results in a greater temperature drop. The hot water temperature that feeds the absorption chiller ranges from 86.7 to 90.7 °C, whereas the hot

Table 14

Annual results of Upgraded Scenario 3 with 2 TES tanks, 1 hot water tank of 50 m³ for the biodiesel units, and 1 cooling storage tank at the digester for various cooling tank volumes.

Hot water storage tank volume for the biodiesel units (m ³)	50	50	50	50	50
Cooling storage tank volume at the digester (m ³)	10	20	30	40	50
ORC heat input (MWh _{th})	20196.6	20196.6	20196.6	20196.6	20196.6
Absorption chiller heat input (MWh _{th})	4345.7	4345.7	4345.7	4345.7	4345.7
ORC electricity production (MWh _{el})	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4
Digester (HT) cooling production (MWh _c)	1359.3	1371.4	1378.4	1381.1	1382.6
Coverage of digester cooling load	93.5 %	94.3 %	94.8 %	95.0 %	95.1 %
Biodiesel (LT) cooling production (MWh _c)	1717.3	1717.3	1717.3	1717.3	1717.3
Coverage of biodiesel cooling load	98.0 %	98.0 %	98.0 %	98.0 %	98.0 %

Table 15

Annual results of Upgraded Scenario 3 with 2 TES tanks, 1 hot water tank of 100 m³ for the biodiesel units, and 1 cooling storage tank at the digester for various cooling tank volumes.

Hot water storage tank volume for the biodiesel units (m ³)	100	100	100	100	100
Cooling storage tank volume at the digester (m ³)	10	20	30	40	50
ORC heat input (MWh _{th})	20196.6	20196.6	20196.6	20196.6	20196.6
Absorption chiller heat input (MWh _{th})	4341.2	4341.2	4341.2	4341.2	4341.2
ORC electricity production (MWh _{el})	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4
Digester (HT) cooling production (MWh _c)	1358.8	1371.1	1378.1	1380.9	1382.3
Coverage of digester cooling load	93.4 %	94.3 %	94.8 %	95.0 %	95.1 %
Biodiesel (LT) cooling production (MWh _c)	1716.8	1716.8	1716.8	1716.8	1716.8
Coverage of biodiesel cooling load	98.0 %	98.0 %	98.0 %	98.0 %	98.0 %

water temperature at the ORC inlet is about 100 °C. Moreover, Fig. 9 proves that the increase of the ORC hot water flow rate increases both the heat input to the engine and the ORC electricity production. These results are reasonable and acceptable.

Fig. 10 depicts the performance of the absorption chiller for different ORC hot water flow rates. Specifically, it is obvious that the heat input to the absorption chiller is maximized when the ORC hot water flow rate is equal to 73 m³/h, and in this case, there is a difference in the slope of the cooling production curve. Practically, for higher ORC hot water flow rates, the cooling production load tends to decrease with an increasing rate, while for lower ORC hot water flow rates, the reduction in the cooling load is slight. The maximization of the heat input in the ORC hot water flow rate of 73 m³/h, achieving the value of 614.5 kW_{th}, is explained by the different impacts of various parameters on the heat input in the generator. For lower ORC hot water flow rates, the absorption chiller operates with a higher hot water flow rate and a higher heat source temperature. As a result, it can easily reach the maximum HT cooling capacity of 240 kW_c. On the other hand, the increase of the ORC hot water flow rate results in lower heat input temperature levels in

the absorption chiller. Knowing that the COP decreases when the heat source temperature decreases, the heat input increases, up to the value of 73 m³/h. The required cooling capacity cannot be covered beyond that limit (ORC hot water flow rate of 73 m³/h), and the cooling production load reduces, resulting in the reduction of the heat input load, too. The reduction of the total COP in the range from 70 to 73 m³/h is clearly illustrated in Fig. 11, while the COP after this limit remains approximately constant at 0.71. Finally, Fig. 12 shows the variation of the different temperature levels of the absorption chiller generator and the waste heat stream during this parametric study. Notably, with the increment of the ORC hot water flow rate, the absorption chiller hot water flow rate, and the heat source temperature entering the generator decrease, leading to a lower generator temperature.

When the hot water flow rate that feeds the ORC is equal to its nominal value of 75.5 m³/h, the ORC produces 151.7 kW_{el}, and the absorption chiller produces 191.3 kW_c in the high evaporation temperature (digester load). Furthermore, the hot water stream returns to the CHP units at a temperature of 71.5 °C. However, the hot water flow rate of 73 m³/h is selected to be the final design point for the ORC heat provision. This flow rate is relatively close to the nominal value of 75.5 m³/h, but it leads to a significant increase in the cooling production. Practically, this small reduction in the ORC hot water flow rate leads to a marginal reduction of the ORC power output to 146.7 kW_{el}, while there is a sharp increase in the HT cooling production load at 237.6 kW_c. The reduction in the ORC power production is about 3.3 %, while the increase in the cooling production is 24.2 %. The current Section's parametric analysis demonstrates that setting the ORC hot water flow rate at 73 m³/h allows for optimal absorption chiller sizing. The simulation results for the cases of using both the ORC hot water flow rate of 75.5 m³/h (nominal point), and 73 m³/h (final design point) are presented in Table 8. It is highlighted that the energy conversion efficiency of the ORC is about 6.36 %, which is a reasonable value for low-temperature ORC modules, fed with heat sources at a temperature level of 100 °C [53]. Moreover, the COP of the absorption chiller is computed at 0.71. Finally, the thermophysical properties of all the state points of the ORC and the absorption chiller can be found in Table 9.

Furthermore, a parametric analysis for different ambient temperatures is performed. The variation of the ORC power production is depicted in Fig. 13, and the variation of the HT cooling production is depicted in Fig. 14. The results are reported for different values of the ORC hot water flow rate. Practically, the lower ORC hot water flow rates significantly reduce the ORC power production, while the HT cooling production load is not affected substantially. On the other hand, it is observed that HT cooling production decreases when the ambient temperature rises. When the ambient temperature increases, a higher temperature level at the absorber and the condenser is required, leading to a poorer absorption chiller's COP. Due to its lower COP, the chiller cannot cover the nominal value of the HT cooling load. Lowering the ORC hot water flow rate increases the heat input to the absorption chiller, which may allow the chiller to work more efficiently during hot summer days. However, the performance improvement is marginal. Therefore, there is no compelling reason to reduce the final selected value of 73 m³/h for the ORC hot water flow rate, as such a reduction would not effectively address the poor performance of the absorption chiller at higher temperatures and would also result in a significant decrease in electricity production. Finally, it is underlined that it is essential to explore innovative ways to enhance absorption chiller performance, such as the integration of a cold water TES tank, to be utilized at elevated ambient temperatures.

3.2. Dynamic analysis of the baseline scenario

The Baseline Scenario is investigated under dynamic conditions throughout the year in this section. The hot water flow rate that feeds the ORC remains constant at 73 m³/h. During the dynamic analysis, a solar field of about 45 collectors, which are arranged into 9 strings, is

Fig. 20. HT evaporator load, digester cooling load, and LT (biodiesel) cooling load during the year for Upgraded Scenario 3 with 2 TES tanks, 1 hot water tank volume of 50 m³ for the biodiesel units, and 1 cooling storage tank volume of 30 m³ for the digester.

Fig. 21. HT evaporator load, digester cooling load, and LT (biodiesel) cooling load during the 20th and 21st of July for Upgraded Scenario 3 with 2 TES tanks, 1 hot water tank volume of 50 m³ for the biodiesel units, and 1 cooling storage tank volume of 30 m³ for the digester.

considered. The total aperture area is equal to 88.2 m², as each collector has an area of 1.96 m², while the solar TES tank volume is considered at 1.1 m³.

The annual results of the dynamic simulation of the Baseline Scenario are presented in Table 10. The annual ORC electricity production is calculated as 1319.4 MWh_{el}, the annual digester (HT) cooling output as 1320.4 MWh_c, and the annual biodiesel (LT) cooling output as 1717.4 MWh_c, assuming uninterrupted operation throughout the year. The temperature of hot water resulting from the mixing of waste heat and solar heat throughout the year is shown in Fig. 15. A small increment of about 0.1–0.2 K is achieved through the integration of solar thermal collectors, as the heat produced by them is significantly lower than the available waste heat. Moreover, the ORC power output during the year is

illustrated in Fig. 16, observing that the ORC electricity production is greater in the winter than in the summer. In higher ambient temperature levels, the ORC condensation temperature increases, leading to a smaller expansion work in the expander. Furthermore, the HT (digester) and LT (biodiesel) cooling loads during the year are shown in Fig. 17. During the summer, when the ambient temperature increases, the temperature of the condenser and the absorber of the chiller also increase, leading to a lower COP. Therefore, the absorption chiller can provide cooling loads lower than the nominal values, particularly for the digester, as the biodiesel cooling load is set as a priority. The cooling load coverage is determined to be 90.8 % for the digester and 98.0 % for the biodiesel, on an annual basis.

In addition, the hot water temperature at the inlet and the outlet of

Table 16

Annual results of Upgraded Scenario 4 with 2 TES tanks, 1 hot water tank volume of 50 m³ for the biodiesel units, and 1 cooling storage tank volume of 30 m³ at the digester for various solar collectors' areas.

Annual results	Default area Solar area of 88.2 m ² (45 collectors)	Double area Solar area of 176.4 m ² (90 collectors in total, 45 new)	Fourfold area Solar area of 352.8 m ² (180 collectors in total, 135 new)	Sixfold area Solar area of 529.2 m ² (270 collectors in total, 225 new)
Solar storage tank volume (m ³)	1.1	2.2	4.4	6.6
Hot water storage tank volume for the biodiesel units (m ³)	50	50	50	50
Cooling storage tank volume at the digester (m ³)	30	30	30	30
Available waste heat (MWh _{th})	28790.0	28790.0	28790.0	28790.0
Available solar irradiation (MWh _{th})	145.3	290.7	581.3	872.0
Solar useful heat (MWh _{th})	84.1	161.6	292.7	395.1
Biodiesel heat input (MWh _{th})	3581.1	3581.1	3581.1	3581.1
ORC heat input (MWh _{th})	20196.6	20234.1	20302.9	20355.8
Absorption chiller heat input (MWh _{th})	4345.7	4352.5	4362.5	4369.9
ORC electricity production (MWh _{el})	1319.4	1322.5	1328.4	1332.9
Digester (HT) cooling production (MWh _c)	1378.4	1379.8	1382.1	1384.6
Coverage of digester cooling load	94.8 %	94.9 %	95.0 %	95.2 %
Biodiesel (LT) cooling production (MWh _c)	1717.3	1719.2	1721.9	1723.3
Coverage of biodiesel cooling load	98.0 %	98.1 %	98.3 %	98.4 %

various systems during the year is depicted in Fig. 18. The hot water feeding temperatures are equal to about 100 °C and 88.2 °C for the ORC and the absorption chiller, respectively. The temperature exiting the absorption chiller demonstrates considerable fluctuation between 70–85 °C, revealing the fluctuations in operating conditions during the summer, as the temperatures of the absorber, the condenser, and the generator vary. On the other hand, the hot water temperature exiting the ORC remains consistently about 72 °C throughout the year, indicating a controlled and anticipated performance of the ORC heat recovery

system. Finally, the HT (digester) cooling load and the LT (biodiesel) cooling load are presented in detail during the 20th and 21st of July in Fig. 19. The HT evaporator obviously cannot provide the entire cooling demand from morning to evening (about 9:00–21:00) during the summer. However, the LT cooling load exhibits minor decreases during daytime hours, as it is a priority for the plant.

3.3. Dynamic analysis of upgraded scenarios with multiple storage tanks

In this section, various configurations that integrate storage tanks are presented and analyzed. These configurations include all the systems and the heat requirements of the Baseline Scenario, i.e. the ORC, the absorption chillers, the solar collectors, as well as the biodiesel thermal load, and the piping thermal losses. The integration of both hot and cold storage tanks is examined comprehensively. Especially, the hot water storage tanks focus on the available waste heat management, the productivity enhancement, as well as the proper response to possible interruptions and fluctuations. On the other hand, the concept of cooling storage tanks is suggested as a solution to the poor performance of the absorption chiller when the ambient temperature rises during the summer period. All configurations are evaluated under dynamic conditions throughout a typical year.

3.3.1. Upgraded Scenario 1 with one (1) TES tank for both the biodiesel units and the absorption chiller

The Upgraded Scenario 1 includes a TES tank to feed both the biodiesel units and the absorption chiller. The annual results of this scenario with one (1) TES tank for the biodiesel units, and the absorption chiller for various tank volumes [10, 20, 50, 100, 200, 400] m³ are presented in Table 11. According to the results, the integration of a hot water storage tank is not beneficial for the absorption chiller operation and the cooling production, as both the yearly HT and LT cooling production amounts are smaller compared to the Baseline Scenario. The annual HT and LT cooling yields lie in the range of 1271.4–1281.3 MWh_c, and 1691.2–1711.7 MWh_c, respectively, while the same quantities are computed at 1320.4 MWh_c, and 1717.4 MWh_c, respectively, for the Baseline Scenario. It is important to mention that utilizing a single TES tank for both the biodiesel units and the absorption chiller results in a substantial heat input to the tank, causing a significant temperature difference in the feeding stream (exceeding 20 K). However, the temperature stratification inside the storage tank cannot achieve such HT differences between the upper and the lower tank zones. It is highlighted that both the absorption chiller and biodiesel units are fed with a hot water stream that reaches a temperature value of 83 °C. This temperature level is insufficient to feed the systems, particularly the biodiesel units.

3.3.2. Upgraded Scenario 2 with one (1) TES tank for the biodiesel units

The incorporation of a TES tank to feed the biodiesel units is examined in the Upgraded Scenario 2. This analysis is carried out considering different hot water tank volumes [10, 20, 50, 100, 200, 400] m³. The annual results of Upgraded Scenario 2 with one (1) TES tank that feeds the biodiesel units for various tank volumes are presented in Table 12. In the case of using a TES tank volume of 50 m³, the biodiesel units are driven by a hot water temperature of about 93 °C, while the absorption chiller with a temperature level of about 88.5 °C. These temperature levels are acceptable, while the digester (HT) cooling production is about 1352.3 MWh_c per year, which is larger than that of the Baseline Scenario (1320.4 MWh_c). Furthermore, the annual biodiesel (LT) cooling production is calculated at 1717.3 MWh_c. Thus, it is worth mentioning that the integration of a hot water storage tank to feed the biodiesel units improves the performance of the absorption chiller, as the hot water input stream has a slightly higher temperature level than that of the Baseline Scenario.

Furthermore, the autonomous operation of the biodiesel units is investigated, considering that they are driven only by the stored heat

Fig. 22. Hot water temperature after the mixing between waste heat and solar heat during the year for Upgraded Scenario 4 with 2 TES tanks, 1 hot water tank volume of 50 m³ for the biodiesel units, and 1 cooling storage tank volume of 30 m³ at the digester with sixfold solar collectors.

Table 17
Comparative results of different scenarios.

Annual results	Baseline Scenario	Upgraded Scenario 1	Upgraded Scenario 2	Upgraded Scenario 3	Upgraded Scenario 4
Hot water storage tank volume for both the biodiesel units and the absorption chiller (m ³)	–	50	–	–	–
Hot water storage tank volume for the biodiesel units (m ³)	–	–	50	50	50
Cooling storage tank volume at the digester (m ³)	–	–	–	30	30
Solar field area (m ²)	88.2	88.2	88.2	88.2	529.2
Solar storage tank volume (m ³)	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1	6.6
Available waste heat (MWh _{th})	28790.0	28790.0	28790.0	28790.0	28790.0
Available solar irradiation (MWh _{th})	145.3	145.3	145.3	145.3	872.0
Solar useful heat (MWh _{th})	84.0	84.0	84.0	84.1	395.1
Biodiesel heat input (MWh _{th})	3581.1	3581.1	3581.1	3581.1	3581.1
ORC heat input (MWh _{th})	20197.1	20197.1	20197.1	20196.6	20355.8
Absorption chiller heat input (MWh _{th})	3664.2	3600.8	3700.4	4345.7	4369.9
ORC electricity production (MWh _{el})	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4	1319.4	1332.9
Digester (HT) cooling production (MWh _c)	1320.4	1271.4	1352.3	1378.4	1384.6
Coverage of digester cooling load	90.8 %	87.4 %	93.0 %	94.8 %	95.2 %
Biodiesel (LT) cooling production (MWh _c)	1717.4	1709.6	1717.3	1717.3	1723.3
Coverage of biodiesel cooling load	98.0 %	97.6 %	98.0 %	98.0 %	98.4 %

inside the hot water tank and are not fed with heat from the CHP units or the solar collectors. This solution can be applied in case of an accident or a shutdown. The results of the analysis of the autonomous biodiesel operation for various tank volumes and temperature limits are found in Table 13. The biodiesel units are presumed to be supplied with a hot water stream at a temperature of no less than 87 °C. An autonomous biodiesel operation lasting around 0.5 to 1.5 h may be anticipated when utilizing hot water tank volumes of about 50–100 m³.

3.3.3. Upgraded Scenario 3 with two (2) TES tanks, one (1) for the biodiesel units, and one (1) for cooling storage at the digester

Taking into account the results of the previous two subsections, where two different configurations include hot water storage tanks to feed the biodiesel units, and/or the absorption chiller, it can be mentioned that the consideration of the biodiesel hot water tank is more beneficial thermodynamically and enhances the performance of the cooling system. In this section, a new configuration, which integrates not only a biodiesel hot water tank but also a cooling storage tank, is examined. According to the dynamic results of the Baseline Scenario, during the summer period, especially during the noon hours, when the ambient temperature increases significantly, the absorption chiller cannot provide the digester’s nominal cooling load (166.4 kW_c).

However, during the night hours, the absorption cycle operates effectively at the full load. To address the challenge of daytime performance fluctuations, the implementation of a cooling storage tank is proposed. This system would reduce the variability in the absorption chiller’s output during the day by storing cooling energy in the form of chilled water produced at night. This stored cooling capacity can be exploited during the day when the absorption chiller works at partial load. In the Upgraded Scenario 3, it is assumed that the absorption chiller HT evaporator works with the maximum cooling load of 240.0 kW_c during the night, to meet the nominal load of digester cooling (166.4 kW_c), while the excess load is stored in the tank to be used during the day. The annual results of this scenario with 2 TES tanks, one (1) for the biodiesel units and one (1) for cooling storage at the digester for various cooling tank volumes [10,20,30,40,50] m³ are presented in detail in Tables 14, and 15, for a biodiesel hot water tank volume of 50 m³, and 100 m³, respectively. The aforementioned biodiesel hot water tank volumes are considered more thermodynamically efficient and anticipated to be more economically viable compared with storage tanks of greater sizes.

In the case of using a TES tank volume of 50 m³ for the biodiesel units, and a cooling storage tank volume of 30 m³, the cooling storage tank covers the digester cooling demand in full load (166.4 kW_c) by 94.8 % during the year. This means that the coverage of the digester’s cooling

Fig. 23. Annual production increment compared to the Baseline Scenario for the ORC electricity production, digester (HT) cooling production, and biodiesel (LT) cooling production for all the examined Upgraded Scenarios.

Table 18

Simple payback period levels, as well as the annual production increments compared to the Baseline Scenario for the ORC electricity production, the digester (HT) cooling production, and the biodiesel (LT) cooling production for Upgraded Scenarios 2, 3, and 4.

Scenario	Simple payback period of the tanks (years)	Electricity production increment compared to the Baseline Scenario	Digester cooling increment compared to the Baseline Scenario	LT-biodiesel cooling increment compared to the Baseline Scenario
Upgraded Scenario 2 – Various hot water tank volumes for the biodiesel units				
$V_{\text{tank}} = 10 \text{ m}^3$	–	0.0 %	–0.2 %	0.0 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 20 \text{ m}^3$	10.1	0.0 %	2.2 %	0.0 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 50 \text{ m}^3$	14.6	0.0 %	2.4 %	0.0 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 100 \text{ m}^3$	30.6	0.0 %	2.2 %	0.0 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 200 \text{ m}^3$	90.5	0.0 %	2.0 %	–0.1 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 400 \text{ m}^3$	–	0.0 %	1.2 %	–0.1 %
Upgraded Scenario 3 – Biodiesel hot water tank volume of 50 m^3 and various cooling storage tank volumes				
$V_{\text{tank}} = 10 \text{ m}^3$	18.4	0.0 %	2.9 %	0.0 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 20 \text{ m}^3$	15.1	0.0 %	3.9 %	0.0 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 30 \text{ m}^3$	14.1	0.0 %	4.4 %	0.0 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 40 \text{ m}^3$	14.4	0.0 %	4.6 %	0.0 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 50 \text{ m}^3$	15.0	0.0 %	4.7 %	0.0 %
Upgraded Scenario 3 – Biodiesel hot water tank volume of 100 m^3 and various cooling storage tank volumes				
$V_{\text{tank}} = 10 \text{ m}^3$	29.4	0.0 %	2.9 %	0.0 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 20 \text{ m}^3$	22.6	0.0 %	3.8 %	0.0 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 30 \text{ m}^3$	20.5	0.0 %	4.4 %	0.0 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 40 \text{ m}^3$	20.5	0.0 %	4.6 %	0.0 %
$V_{\text{tank}} = 50 \text{ m}^3$	21.1	0.0 %	4.7 %	0.0 %
Upgraded Scenario 4– Biodiesel hot water tank volume of 50 m^3 and cooling storage tank volume of 30 m^3				
Solar area of 176.4 m^2 (90 collectors)	22.4	0.2 %	4.5 %	0.1 %
Solar area of 352.8 m^2 (180 collectors)	34.6	0.7 %	4.7 %	0.3 %
Solar area of 529.2 m^2 (270 collectors)	46.3	1.0 %	4.9 %	0.3 %

load has increased by 4.0 % in comparison with the Baseline Scenario. According to the results, the digester (HT) cooling production is determined at 1378.4 MWh_c per year, surpassing the Baseline Scenario's output of 1320.4 MWh_c . The yearly results of the HT evaporator load, the digester cooling load, and the LT (biodiesel) cooling load are shown in Fig. 20. It is important to note that the distribution of the HT evaporator load supplying the cooling storage tank exhibits greater

variability compared to that of the digester cooling load. This indicates the potential of the cooling storage tank to mitigate performance fluctuations and provide higher cooling production loads. On the other hand, the LT cooling load appears to have smaller reductions during the day hours, as it is a priority for the industry. The HT evaporator load, the digester cooling load, and the LT (biodiesel) cooling load are presented in detail during the 20th and 21st of July in Fig. 21. Fig. 21 indicates that

the HT evaporator cannot provide the full load from morning (about 9 a.m.) to evening hours (about 10p.m.). However, the cooling storage tank can provide the digester's nominal cooling load (166.4 kW_c) not only during the night, but also during the hours around noon and the afternoon, as this tank has stored chilled water at night. To sum up, the incorporation of a cold water storage tank at the digester enhances the cooling production performance.

3.3.4. Upgraded Scenario 4 with two (2) TES tanks, one (1) for the biodiesel units, and 1 for cooling storage at the digester with additional solar collectors

The integration of additional solar thermal collectors to provide more useful heat into the plant processes is investigated in the Upgraded Scenario 4. Three cases are examined, considering double (2), fourfold (4), and sixfold (6) solar collectors' areas compared to the initially proposed area. As the collectors' area increases, the volume of solar TES tanks must also increase. During this analysis, one (1) TES tank volume of 50 m³ for the biodiesel units and one (1) cooling storage tank volume of 30 m³ for the digester are assumed. The annual results of the cases with increased solar collectors' areas can be found in Table 16. The installation of additional solar collectors does not appear to substantially improve the production or the performance of the integrated systems. Utilizing six times more solar collectors than the Baseline Scenario results in a marginal increase in yearly ORC electricity production, HT-digester cooling production, and LT-biodiesel cooling by up to 1.02 %, 0.45 %, and 0.35 %, respectively. Furthermore, the hot water temperature after the mixing of waste heat and solar heat during the year is shown in Fig. 22. According to this figure, the hot water achieves temperature levels up to about 101.5 °C, leading to small increments in the hot water feeding temperatures.

3.4. Comparison and discussion of the different scenarios

The outcomes of the Baseline Scenario as well as the results of one case of all the Upgraded Scenarios presented in Section 3.3 (Upgraded Scenarios 1–4), are compared and discussed in this section. First, comparing the scenarios of Sections 3.3.1 and 3.3.2 (Upgraded Scenarios 1 & 2) that include only hot water storage tanks with the Baseline Scenario, Upgraded Scenario 2 in Section 3.3.2 which integrates a hot water tank only for the biodiesel units, seems to perform better thermodynamically. Applying this concept, a small improvement of 2.4 % in the yearly digester cooling production is achieved in comparison with the Baseline Scenario (1352.3 against 1320.4 MWh_c). In parallel, annual biodiesel cooling production is practically not affected by this implementation (1717.3 against 1717.4 MWh_c), and the biodiesel units are fed at a sufficient temperature level (about 93 °C). However, Upgraded Scenario 1 results in inferior performance, with the digester and biodiesel cooling production decreasing by 3.7 % and 0.5 % per year, respectively. The hot water storage tank for the biodiesel units appears to enhance overall thermodynamic performance, enabling possible independent operation of around 0.5 to 1.5 h. In addition to this, a cold water storage tank is applied to enhance the cooling production performance in Upgraded Scenario 3. The yearly digester cooling production is enhanced by 4.4 % compared to the Baseline Scenario (1378.4 against 1320.4 MWh_c), integrating small-scale storage tanks, i.e., 1 hot water tank volume of 50 m³ for the biodiesel units, and 1 cooling storage tank volume of 30 m³. Upgraded Scenario 3, which is presented in detail in Section 3.3.3, demonstrates superior thermodynamic performance compared to the other Upgraded Scenarios. Finally, in Upgraded Scenarios 1, 2, and 3, the ORC electricity yield remains almost constant.

It is essential to state that installing additional solar thermal collectors in Upgraded Scenario 4 is not profitable, as a minor increment in both the electricity and cooling production is achieved, even in the case of a sixfold collector area compared to the baseline area. The outcomes of all the examined scenarios are presented comparatively in Table 17, while the annual production increment compared to the Baseline

Scenario for the ORC electricity production, the digester (HT) cooling production, and the biodiesel (LT) cooling production for all the examined Upgraded Scenarios are illustrated in Fig. 23. Overall, the scenario with two TES tanks, one with a capacity of 50 m³ for the biodiesel units and another with a capacity of 30 m³ for cooling storage at the digester, achieves the best thermodynamic performance among the examined scenarios.

In addition, the economic analysis of Upgraded Scenarios 2, 3, and 4 is carried out, determining the payback periods for the integrated storage tanks. These scenarios involve different storage tank capacities and solar collector areas. The simple payback period levels of Upgraded Scenarios 2, 3, and 4, along with the annual production increments compared to the Baseline Scenario for the ORC electricity production, the digester (HT) cooling production, and the biodiesel (LT) cooling production, can be found in Table 18. The Upgraded Scenario 1 is omitted due to its inferior thermodynamic performance in comparison with the Baseline Scenario.

First, regarding the Upgraded Scenario 2, the case with a biodiesel hot water tank volume of 20 m³ is the only tank size with a relatively moderate simple payback period of 10.1 years. The case of using a biodiesel hot water tank volume of 50 m³ has a longer payback period of 14.6 years. Furthermore, the Upgraded Scenario 3 with a hot water tank volume of 50 m³ for the biodiesel units is analyzed. As the cooling tank size increases, the payback period decreases slightly. The best economic performance within this range is determined for the case of using a cold water tank of 30 m³, achieving the shortest payback period of 14.1 years. Finally, the Upgraded Scenario 4 is investigated. Increasing the solar area consistently increases both the capital cost and the payback period. All the cases of Upgraded Scenario 4 have very long payback periods, ranging from 22.4 to 46.3 years, making them economically unattractive.

Therefore, the Upgraded Scenario 2, with a biodiesel hot water tank volume of 20 m³ is the most economically feasible case, as it has the shortest payback period. In addition, Upgraded Scenario 3 cases achieve slightly longer payback periods than Upgraded Scenario 2. However, these options may still be viable for the industrial plant when considering non-economic factors, such as operational or strategic priorities. If minimizing the payback period is not the sole criterion in the techno-economic evaluation, it would be advantageous for the plant to also consider Upgraded Scenario 3, which includes the integration of a cooling storage tank volume of 30 m³.

4. Conclusions

The purpose of the present work is the analysis and design of a polygeneration system to cover the energy needs of a biofuels plant. The configuration produces electricity through an ORC, useful heat to feed the biodiesel reactors, and cooling at two different temperature levels via an absorption cycle. The system's driving force is the available waste heat in the form of hot water, assisted by solar thermal collectors. Various TES solutions are evaluated and compared thermodynamically and economically. The fundamental conclusions of the present study are listed below:

- The parametric investigation of the Baseline Scenario on steady-state conditions reveals that an ORC hot water flow rate of 73 m³/h leads to an increased digester cooling capacity by 24.2 %, with a small reduction in the ORC power output, in comparison to the nominal operating conditions (ORC hot flow rate of 75.5 m³/h).
- The annual simulation study of the Baseline Scenario indicates an annual ORC electricity production of 1319.4 MWh_{el}, a digester cooling production of 1320.4 MWh_c, and a biodiesel cooling production of 1717.4 MWh_c.
- The integration of a hot water storage tank to feed the biodiesel units seems to be beneficial thermodynamically, increasing the digester cooling yield and serving as a backup unit.

- The scenario that incorporates two thermal energy storage tanks, a hot water volume of 50 m³ for the biodiesel units, and a cooling storage tank volume of 30 m³ at the digester outperforms in terms of thermodynamics compared to the other examined scenarios.
- This scenario achieves an annual digester cooling output of 1378.4 MWh_c, increased by 4.4 %, compared to the Baseline Scenario, whereas the digester cooling coverage is determined at 94.8 %, and the payback period at 14.1 years.
- The integration of a cooling storage tank significantly improves the digester cooling performance, providing a strategic operation solution for the plant.
- The best techno-economic performance is achieved when a hot water storage volume of 20 m³ is applied to feed the biodiesel units, reaching a payback period of 10.1 years.
- The contribution of the additional solar thermal collectors to the system productivity is marginal and not economically beneficial.

Future research should concentrate on the environmental analysis and the dynamic optimization of the proposed system. Additionally,

researchers should carry out simulation studies considering variable heat and cooling demand profiles. Finally, the integration of the proposed technologies into different industrial plants may be examined.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Plant processes analysis and data collection

This appendix provides an overview of the analysis and data collection conducted at the MIL OIL plant during three critical periods: March, July, and December 2023. The primary objective is to evaluate the plant's thermal and cooling needs. Real-time operational data are collected from the two CHP units, CHP1 and CHP2, as well as the digester's cooling system during March, July, and December. The data collection spans extended timeframes (March 1–15, July 1–30, and December 1–31) and covers the entire daily operations. Measurements, recorded every two seconds and averaged every five minutes to ensure accuracy, include outlet and return temperatures of the hot water circuits. These data are used to calculate temperature differences and consequently thermal loads.

The analysis reveals significant seasonal variations in thermal loads. In March, the mean total thermal load is 118.7 kW_{th}, with CHP1 contributing 92.4 kW_{th} and CHP2 providing 26.3 kW_{th}. By July, the total thermal load had increased to 212.3 kW_{th}, largely driven by a higher contribution from CHP2 (139.2 kW_{th}). In December, the total thermal load decreases to 176.2 kW_{th}, with CHP1 and CHP2 contributing 111.9 kW_{th} and 64.3 kW_{th}, respectively. Notably, the total thermal load of the two existing CHP units includes the thermal load that feeds the biodiesel units and the piping thermal losses.

Next, the piping system connecting the CHP units to the biodiesel reactors and storage tanks plays a critical role in heat distribution. The total length of the piping network is approximately 245 m, with an external maximum diameter of 18 cm, including a 5 cm insulation layer. The insulation material, assumed to have a thermal conductivity of 0.04 W/(m K) [54], is used to calculate thermal resistance and heat transfer coefficients. The analysis determines a total thermal resistance of 0.014 K/W and an overall heat transfer coefficient (U) of 0.52 W/m²K. The piping UA-value, a measure of heat transfer efficiency, is calculated at 70.73 W/K. Furthermore, it is underlined that seasonal variations also affect thermal losses. For example, piping thermal losses are moderate (5.8 kW_{th}) in March due to a mean ambient temperature of 9.7 °C, lower (4.6 kW_{th}) in July with a mean ambient temperature of 26.5 °C, and higher (6.1 kW_{th}) in December with a mean ambient temperature of 4.8 °C.

In addition, the biodiesel production line consists of four reactors and associated tanks. The reactors operate in six-hour batch cycles, with heating demands peaking during the two-hour distillation phase of production. An average thermal load of 163.5 kW_{th} is estimated. This load is calculated by subtracting piping losses from the total thermal output of the CHP units. However, future expansion plans include the installation of six additional biodiesel reactors. This expansion is projected to increase the biodiesel thermal load by 250 %, reaching 408.8 kW_{th}. The mean values of biodiesel thermal load along with the piping thermal losses and the mean values of total thermal load, in March, July, and December 2023, are shown in Fig. A.1.

In parallel, the cooling loads are also estimated. The biodiesel cooling load is taken directly from industry. On the other hand, the plant's digester cooling system is based on a cold water circuit with glycol. The nominal flow rate of the cooling system is 30 m³/h, while the cold water with glycol exhibits a density of 1010 kg/m³ and a specific heat capacity of 3.7 kJ/(kg K). Finally, it is noted that the peak cooling load is recorded at 166.4 kW_c.

Fig. A.1. Mean values of biodiesel, and total thermal load, along with the piping thermal losses in March, July, and December 2023.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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